

pH-metric, Spectral, Magnetic and Thermal Investigation on Ni-2-hydroxy-3-(3-methyl-2-butenyl)-1, 4-naphthoquinone (Lapachol) Complex

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$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the nickel-lapachol complex based upon pH-metric, thermal studies is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 4.5$ B.M.) and non-electrolytic in nature. The protonation constant of lapachol and stability constants of nickel complex at 20° and 40° have been determined, employing Irving-Rossotti technique. The thermodynamic parameters are also reported. Spectral data suggest the participation of hydroxyl and carbonyl groups in complexation.

Desolvation of hydrated nickel-lapachol chelate, studied employing D.T.A. curve and Borchardt and Daniels equation is kinetically first order reaction. Activation energy of solid state reaction is 4250 cal/mole.

METAL complexes of lapachol are little studied¹. Sawhney and Vohra² investigated recently indicator properties of lapachol. pH-metric, magnetic, spectral and thermal studies of nickel complex are reported in this communication.

Experimental

All the inorganic chemicals were of analytical grade. Lapachol was obtained from M/s Aldrich Co., U.S.A. Approximately 0.1M NiCl₂ was prepared in water and standardised complexometrically. Lapachol (0.01M) solution was prepared by dissolving weighed amount of it in Et.OH. All pH measurements were made with Backman pH-meter. Correction for 50% Et.OH-water system was applied due to Uiter and Hass³. For practical proton ligand stability constant (P_bH) and stability constants of the complex, three solutions (total volume 50 ml) were pH-metrically titrated with 0.02M KOH at 20° and 40° at $\mu = 0.2M$ KCl. 50% Et.OH-water system was kept as medium.

(i) $4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ HCl. (ii) $4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ HCl.,
 $1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ Lapachol

(iii) $4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ HCl., $1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ Lapachol.,
 $2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ Ni²⁺

Also different metal ligand molar ratio of 0:1, 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 were titrated to arrive at certain composition of complex.

The magnetic susceptibility measurement was carried out on Cahn Faraday Magnetic Susceptibility

Electrobalance (Model 7550, Calif., U.S.A.). Mercuric tetrathiocyanato(II) was used as calibrant. The manually operated thermogravimetric measurement apparatus was used. The thermogram, heating rate being fairly constant approximately 7°/minute, of the complex was obtained by using sample of air dried complex. Calcium oxalate was used as calibrant. For D.T.A. of nickel-lapachol complex, Differential Thermal Apparatus (D.T.A-2-Universal), (Manufacturers-VEB Laborelaktstre 5, G.D.R.) was used for analysis. The i.r. spectra in KBr pellet was recorded on Perkin Elmer Infracord Spectrophotometer. For C. H. analysis, thermo electric equipment (THERELEK) was employed.

Isolation of complex :

Lapachol solution prepared in one equivalent KOH was added slowly with constant stirring to solution containing nickel ions. The red precipitate was filtered, washed with ice-cooled water and dried at 60-70°.

Complex	C%	H%	Ni%
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$	61.46 (61.96)	5.29 (4.94)	10.02 (11.22)

Experimental data are given in parentheses.

Results and Discussion

Nickel-lapachol complex is powder in solid state, slightly soluble in water and ethanol. It is an indication

that the complex is not polymeric like those of naphthazarin and 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone^{4,5}.

Values of formation functions \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pA were calculated using expressions given by Irving and Rossotti⁶. Plot of $-\log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A}$ versus pH yielded the value of P_kH . The metal ligand stability constants have been obtained by the methods of use of mid point, correction term⁷. To minimise the error, the method of interpolation at half \bar{n} values⁸ was avoided as the difference between $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ was less than 2.5. The values of overall changes in free energy ΔG° , enthalpy ΔH° and entropy ΔS° have been determined by using wellknown temperature coefficient and Gibb's Helmholtz equation. Table I incorporates the values of P_kH , $\log k_1$, $\log k_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ and thermodynamic functions. The free energy of formation (ΔG°) of complex have more negative value with the increase of temperature, indicating that complex formation is a spontaneous process. The enthalpy is negative for complex which is favourable for the formation of the complex. ΔS° is +ve, favouring the complex formation.

TABLE I—PROTONATION CONSTANT OF LAPACHOL, STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF NICKEL-LAPACHOL COMPLEX

Protonation constant/stability constant	Temperature (°C)	ΔG° (Kcals/mole)		ΔH° (Kcals/mole)	ΔS° (cal/mole/°C)
		20°C	40°C		
Log P_kH	6.45	5.69			
Log k_1	A	4.16	3.99		
	B	3.87	3.81		
	C	(4.02)	(3.90)		
Log K_2	A	3.51	3.65		
	B	3.81	3.21		
	C	3.16	3.47		
Log k_1/k_2	C	+0.86	+0.43		
Log β_2	A	7.67	7.64	-10.28	-10.96
	B	7.68	7.02		-0.63
	C	7.18	7.39		+33.05

- A = "Correction Term" method
- B = Use of mid-point method
- C = Method of Interpolation at half \bar{n} values

The value of \bar{n} approaches 2 for the complex. It indicates the existence of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. pH -metric titrations of different metal-ligand molar ratio of 0:1, 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 show that the reaction between nickel and lapachol takes place with the liberation of protons, the limiting condition being reached with metal-ligand molar ratio of 1:2. Afterwards overlapping of curves takes place, indicating that a maximum of two protons can be liberated in the reaction per metal ion. This supports the existence of 1:2 metal to ligand complex.

With the appearance of broad absorption band in the spectra of complex, in the 3400 cm^{-1} range, indicative of O-H stretching, presence of lattice water was concluded. Further it has been seen that the strongest peak at 1655 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$) is shifted below showing, thereby, the participation of carbonyl group in complexation. Nickel lapachol complex is paramagnetic ($\mu=4.5\text{ B.M.}$). Probably it is a tetrahedral complex as all those complexes in which ligands are identicals have moments of 3.7–4.0 B.M.

T.G. and D. T. A. studies are very informative. For nickel lapachol complex (Fig. 1), it would appear from T.G. curve that it is stable upto 80° and loses $2\frac{1}{2}\text{ H}_2\text{O}$ from 80° to 140° . Plateau between 140° and 168° corresponds to $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_8)_2$. Further dissociation starts from 168° and completes until 540° ; that plateau between 540° and 740° points to nickel oxide.

Fig. 1. T.G. and D.T.A. curves for Ni-Lapachol complex

Examination of D.T.A. curve (Fig. 1) reveals an endotherm around 150° , corresponding to desolvation of hydrated complex and an exotherm at 450° , referring to dissociation of anhydrous chelate.

Kinetics of solid state reaction of complex employing D.T.A. curve and Borchardt and Daniels^{9,10} equation

$$k = h'/A - a$$

- where, A = Total area under D.T.A. curve,
 - a = Area at time, t,
 - h' = Height of curve at time, t,
 - k = Specific rate constant,
- have been studied.

Desolvation of hydrated complex :

$$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O} (\text{S}) \xrightarrow{\text{heat}} \text{Ni}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3)_2 (\text{S}) + 2\frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O} (\text{vapour})$$
 is of first order^{1,1,2}. Plot of $\ln k$ (calculated with Borchardt and Daniels equation) versus the reciprocal of absolute temperature yielded a straight line, confirming thereby the reaction under investigation to be of first order reaction. Activation energy of the reaction calculated from the slope of the curve is 4250 cal/mole (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Borchardt and Daniel's Plot.

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